

Establishing Rapport in Education: Standpoint of Low-Income Families

Jocy Alcaria Carillo

Abstract. This study aimed to investigate and understand low-income families' unique experiences and coping mechanisms. The participants in this study were ten parents of students from Osmeña Elementary School and underwent an In-Depth Interview. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the researcher collected first-hand narratives about low-income families' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights regarding parental involvement in their children's education. The study participants were ten (10) parents of students enrolled at a school in Compostela West division of Davao de Oro, identified as low-income families and willing to participate. Extracted narratives from the interview revealed the experiences of low-income families: financial stress and working more jobs. The findings showed the experiences of low-income families regarding parental involvement in education and the emergence of the two themes: financial stress and discouraged by their educational attainment. On the other hand, the coping mechanisms of parents from low-income families and the emergence of the two themes: attending PTA meetings and the brigada eskwela program and working more jobs. Finally, the insights formulated are strategic parenting, time management, and working on family-oriented projects. Some things are easier said than done; in the case of low-income families, their socioeconomic status immensely influenced their involvement. But there was a plethora of ways that would enable us to show support for the academe. It would indeed take a village to raise a child.

KEY WORDS

1. low income 2. standpoint 3. rapport 4. financial stress

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 1, 2024

1. Introduction

The degree of parental involvement in a child's education is a crucial variable that greatly impacts the student's academic performance and overall educational experience. Its implications assume bigger significance within the context of low-income families in the Philippines. This subject is of utmost significance for the Philippine educational system since low-income families frequently have specific challenges that can make it difficult to actively participate in their children's education. Recent global studies have underscored the critical impact of parental involvement on student success. Schleicher (2018) demonstrated that students whose parents are actively engaged in their education tend to perform better academically. Schleicher's study showed that reading together, discussing school events, and foster-

ing educational aspirations significantly boost students' academic performance and motivation. This report emphasizes the need for educational systems worldwide to create frameworks that support and enhance parental engagement in schools. Moreover, a comprehensive meta-analysis by Wilder (2020) provides a deeper understanding of the forms and impacts of parental involvement. Wilder's research indicates that home-based involvement, such as assisting with homework, and school-based involvement, such as attending school events, contribute positively to student outcomes. Home-based involvement was found to significantly improve literacy and numeracy skills, while school-based involvement was more effective in enhancing students' social skills and overall school attendance. Wilder's findings advocate for a balanced approach that integrates home and school activities to optimize the benefits of parental involvement. In terms of cultural differences, Yamamoto and Holloway (2019) compared parental involvement across different countries, revealing that cultural norms and educational policies shape how parents participate in their children's education. In Asian cultures, where there is a strong emphasis on academic achievement and structured support, parental involvement often includes rigorous academic supervision. Conversely, in many Western cultures, parental involvement focuses more on fostering independence and critical thinking. Yamamoto and Holloway's study underscores the importance of culturally sensitive approaches to parental engagement that respect and leverage local norms and values to enhance educational outcomes globally. Meanwhile, studies in the Philippines have also highlighted the significant role of parental involvement in the academic success and overall development of students. San Antonio and Gamage (2019) found that students whose parents were actively involved in school activities, such as attending parent-teacher meetings and participating in school events, exhibited higher academic achievement and better social behavior. The researchers emphasized that fostering strong school-family partnerships is crucial for enhancing student outcomes in the Philippines. Another notable study by Bernardo and Esteban (2020) examined the impact of home-based parental involvement on students' academic performance in the Philippines. They highlighted the importance of providing parents with the necessary resources and training to effectively support their children's education at home, suggesting that schools should develop programs to equip parents with these skills. Furthermore, cultural factors also play a crucial role in shaping parental involvement in the Philippines. Bautista et. al (2021), investigated how cultural values influence parental engagement practices. They discovered that Filipino parents often emphasize the importance of education and academic excellence, driven by a cultural belief in education as a pathway to better opportunities. However, the study also noted challenges such as economic constraints and limited educational attainment among parents, which can hinder their ability to support their children effectively. Bautista and colleagues recommended that schools implement culturally sensitive strategies that address these barriers, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of parental involvement in the educational process. In the local landscape, Perez and Alvarez (2021) exposed the economic and cultural factors influencing parental involvement. Their research focused on the barriers faced by parents in Davao City, including economic hardships and time constraints due to work commitments. Despite these challenges, the study found that Filipino cultural values, which place a high importance on education, motivated parents to engage in their children's schooling as much as possible. Despite the wealth of research on parental involvement in education, there remains a noticeable gap in the literature concerning the specific challenges, strategies,

and outcomes associated with parental involvement among low-income families in Philippine public schools. Even though there is a wealth of study on parental involvement in education, there is a glaring research gap when it comes to knowing the particular difficulties, solutions, and results of parental engagement in the setting of low-income families enrolled in public schools in the Philippines. There is an urgent need for research that focuses on the unique socioeconomic circumstances of low-income Filipino families and how these factors shape the nature and efficacy of their involvement in their children's education, even though existing studies provide insightful information about parental involvement in a variety of settings. It is crucial to fill this research gap because it can guide the creation of policies and procedures supports educational equity and enhance outcomes for this vulnerable demographic. This study was conceptualized based on the existing research gap. In the district of Compostela West in Davao de Oro, many children belong to low-income families. This adds more challenges both to the students and parents when it comes to the child's education. This phenomenological study's goal is to learn more about the real-life experiences of low-income parents in the Philippines regarding their engagement in their children's education within the public school system as well as the factors that affect their active participation in their child's education. The findings of the study added depth to the existing

body of knowledge about parental involvement among low-income parents and offer insightful information about educational management. Thus, putting into consideration the cited problem situation, I find it timely and necessary to conduct this study. This has brought me the necessity to conduct a study about parental involvement in education among low-income families in public elementary schools. I hope that this study benefited to identified sectors of the academe. This includes the educational leaders, school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders can benefit from the findings of this study because it can offer them a fresh point of view in perceiving parental involvement and the perceptions and challenges that come with it. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals to be aware and informed about the socioeconomic background of some students and how it affects their parents' involvement and participation in school. Teachers can benefit from this study by looking into the findings and learning from the experiences and insights that the study uncovered. The internal and external stakeholders may also provide better support to enhance parental involvement in schools. Finally, this would be an additional contribution for future researchers to their references in the field of parental involvement and their socio-economic status, offering them a substantial contribution to their academic arsenal.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study aims to explore and understand the unique experiences and coping mechanisms by low-income parents in the Philippines as they actively participate in and support their children's education within the public school system. This study attempts to provide a thorough knowledge of these parents' daily experiences by revealing their driving forces, the challenges they encounter, and the strategies they use to navigate the challenging educational landscape. The findings of this study helped us understand parental involvement in low-income families in a more nuanced and compassionate way, which helps educational leaders develop interventions and policies specifically aimed at improving educational equity and outcomes in the Philippines. This study intends to significantly expand our understanding of parental participation in low-income families by examining parents' first-

person narratives. The results could provide educational policymakers, school administrators, and professionals in professional development with insightful information. This research aims to foster a deeper understanding of the relationships at play, opening the door for informed decisions and more efficient strategies to increase parental involvement in low-income settings.

1.2. Research Questions—This study sought to uncover the perceptions and challenges regarding parental involvement in education among low-income families. This study was conducted, and the researcher sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of low-income families in terms of parental involvement in education?
- (2) How do families cope with the problems they encountered in their parental involvement of being low-income?
- (3) What moral values can be drawn from the findings of the study to enhance parental involvement among low-income families?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. Parental involvement. It refers to parents' participation in their children's education at home and school. This can take many forms, such as helping with

homework, attending school events and parent-teacher conferences, participating in decision-making processes, or regularly communicating with the child's teacher (Llego, 2022). Low-income. This pertains to not having or earning enough money or resources to make ends meet (Statistics Canada, 2021).

1.4. Significant of the Study—The significance of this study lies in its exploration of the experiences of low-income families with parental involvement in education, their coping mechanisms, and the moral values that can be drawn to enhance such involvement. By examining the experiences of low-income families, the study provides valuable insights into the specific challenges and barriers they face in participating in their children's education. Understanding how these families cope with these

challenges sheds light on effective strategies and resources that can be employed to support and empower them. Additionally, identifying the moral values that emerge from the study offers a framework for developing targeted interventions and support systems that can foster greater parental involvement. Ultimately, the findings have the potential to inform educational policies and practices, promote equity in education, and enhance the overall educational experience for children from low-income families by addressing their unique needs and circumstances.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of the study was anchored on the Parental Involvement Process Theory and model by Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1995). The model allows for three primary mechanisms through which parents, by increasing their involvement in education, can bear an influence on children's educational outcomes. The three

primary mechanisms are modeling, reinforcement, and direct instruction. To give breadth to the construct, modeling predicts that children emulate their parents' behavior by devoting interest and time to activities related to schooling. Reinforcement indicates the mechanism by which parent give their children interest, attention, praise, and rewards related to behaviors

that lead to school success. Finally, parents can influence their children's educational outcomes by direct instruction. As applied in the context of the study, the parental involvement process theory encapsulates the significant concepts of the undertaking conducted. It also reiterates the ways that can enhance parental involvement. The theory predicts that children whose parents are involved in their education are more likely to develop a strong, positive sense of efficacy for successfully achieving school-related tasks than children whose parents are not involved. The study was further reinforced by Walberg's Theory of Academic Achievement (1992). Walberg posited that the psychological characteristics of individual students and their immediate psychological environments influence educational outcomes (cognitive, behavioral, and attitudinal). To add, Walberg's research identified nine key variables that influence educational outcomes: student ability/prior achievement, motivation, age/developmental level, quantity of instruction, quality of instruction, classroom climate, home environment, peer group, and exposure to mass media outside of school. However, the study leans on the aspect that pertains to the student's

home environment. In the context of the study, the theory of academic performance guides the study toward the trial of parental involvement in education among low-income families and how it can affect a student's academic success. Since the lens of this study is focused on low-income families which can also be referred to as the student's home environment, it is important to see how significant its impact on the student's academic success and the parent-teacher partnership is as well. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected variables. The Experiences of Low-Income Parents in terms of Parental Involvement was one of the working themes. And the second Coping mechanism of low-income parents for the problems they encounter. there was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there was a way of exploring the experiences, a way of teaching and learning development that was very critical moral values focused on enhancing parental involvement in low-income families to school success. all these would generate a common intersection.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study's implementation. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study's philosophical and qualitative presumptions were vital in steering the investiga-

tion. Four fundamental assumptions form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

methodological. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher's approach to the study. The philosophical assumption framework was used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Different types of philosophical assumptions were elaborated on. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. A paradigm was a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. Ontology. This section of the study focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. Creswell (2013) asserts that the research participants' perceptions of reality were varied and subjective. This study recognizes the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by parents from low-income families and involvement in their children's education. Every parent's story adds to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. It was my sole responsibility to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of the experiences and coping mechanisms of low-income parents. Epistemology. Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Guba and Lincoln, as referenced by Creswell (2013), the researcher made an effort to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the

participants, I became an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced collection of data. This approach supports the gathering of firsthand experiences and coping mechanisms, which were critical in exploring the subjective realities of the participants. Axiology. It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell (2013), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study was crucial. The values which influence how data were interpreted and presented were explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I handled each participant's narrative with care and integrity, and I always have the utmost respect for the information they provide. This commitment guarantees that the experiences of the parents were communicated truthfully, mirroring both their individual and research values. Methodology. According to Crotty (2020), this was "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures (Wellington, 2015). This study explores the standpoint of low-income families about parental involvement using a qualitative methodology. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, techniques like focus groups and interviews were employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories. These techniques were chosen because they could successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences. Rhetoric. In research, rhetoric was the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions in order to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I utilized an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the voices of the participants while ef-

fectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only made the research easier to read but also guaranteed that

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal was to explore the standpoint of low-income families from Compostela, Davao de Oro. My objective was to gather information about their experiences and coping mechanisms in relation to the phenomenon I am studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I support a level of investigation beyond cursory observations. My research investigated the experiences,

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Determining the precise approach used in a study was crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013) states that studies characterized by verbal rather than statistical analysis are appropriate for qualitative research. Since I studied the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and moral values of low-income families pertaining to parental-involvement the qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that rather than establishing or refuting theories, I describe and elaborate on this phenomenon. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the lived ex-

2.4. *Research Participants*—

the interpretations were strong and based on the experiences of the participants.

challenges, and coping mechanisms of participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasize the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To capture the profound and complex nature of parental-involvement my study places a strong emphasis on in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and moral values related to the parental-involvement, all while upholding phenomenological principles.

periences of the participants in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell (2018), a phenomenological study was a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations. Therefore, my goal was to identify a phenomenon that revolves around the participants' experience pertaining to parental involvement. I collected information from people who have direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to twenty-five, and Morse (1994) suggests at least 6. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, re-

sources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002). The participants in this study consisted of 10 parents of students from Osmeña Elementary School. The 10 participants underwent the In-Depth Interview. These participants were selected based on specific criteria: they need to have children currently enrolled at Osmeña Elementary school, they are identified as low-income parents, and willing to participate in the study. I utilized the purposive sampling design so that the participants are chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2013). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants with respect and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhere to established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluate the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources were directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks,

and benefits. In this research involving students, it was my responsibility to ensure that the participant fully understood the study and their rights. This dual layer of explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the students' autonomy and dignity and ensuring parental consent. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, it was crucial for me to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involves providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modify research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these students was prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it was essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits

associated with participation in a study, as well as to implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assess and balance these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing the safety of participants, particularly considering the vulnerabilities of student participants. This comprehensive approach was crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I am responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures are crucial to protect the privacy of student participants and uphold the integrity of the research process. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of both the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensure that my research is inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strive to make the benefits of the research accessible to all who could benefit from it. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to the reporting of results. In

this study, I offer clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes. Furthermore, I am receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability, not only within the research community but also among the general public. This commitment to openness ensures that the process and results of my research are accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I hold suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provide the foundation to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guarantee access to appropriate facilities for conducting the investigation. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest standards of research integrity and safety. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engage the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and cooperation be-

tween me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helps to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhances the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the

accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employ tools like plagiarism detectors and maintain thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work is devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries are authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I am responsible for ensuring that the research process is conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I created an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings are reliable and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question is satisfactorily addressed and the results are legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allows me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gather information from various sources such as interviews or observations, and I ensure accurate and secure storage of this information. I follow ethical guidelines, safeguard participants' privacy, and ensure data were structured and available

for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helps maintain the integrity of the research process and supports the production of credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyze the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives in accordance with the research query. I utilize meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were not only relevant but also contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I am tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensure the research results are easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they were not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that could further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—

In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. Several steps were taken in adherence to the proper data collection procedure. This was done in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secure endorsements from key stakeholders including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the parents of the participants. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step is scheduled to take place within the first week of October 2023, ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proactive approach not only facilitates compliance with ethical standards but also fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I request permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and the process of participant identification. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was under-

taken during the second week October 2023, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission is granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked permission to conduct the study from the third to the last week of October 2023. Obtaining consent from the participants. With the school heads' approval, I asked consent from the research participants, through informed consent forms that were also provided. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This process ensures that the participants were fully informed and agree to participate. Asking consent from the participants and their parents or guardians was done on the first week of November 2023. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the second week of November 2023. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribe the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure used audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' reactions. The transcription of interviewee responses was scheduled for the third week of November 2023.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories,

subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research

objectives. This process allows me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis was a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis was comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep in-

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I made use of Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences about parental-involvement. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich

sights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I become fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I start categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I create themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes are examined and improved upon to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step entails combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that conveys the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data could also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intricate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. Identifying Sig-

nificant Statements. I carefully identify every statement in the narratives directly related to the phenomenon I am studying. In order to identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step was essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development. Formulating Meanings. After carefully examining the important statements, I determine meanings pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing is never possible, I have to reflexively “bracket” my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants’ real experiences, this process entails putting aside my interpretations as much as was practical. Clustering Themes. I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants’ experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, this preserves the integrity of the analysis. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehen-

sive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it was ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had. Producing the fundamental structure. I break down the lengthy explanation into a succinct, concise statement that highlights the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon’s structure. The essence of the participants’ experiences was effectively and concisely communicated through this succinct synthesis, which concentrates on the essential components that were necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I ask participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased and the analysis was kept firmly based on the perspectives of the participants. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study was about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study was. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba (1981). Credibility. Building credibil-

ity entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility is important for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of sophomore students who participate in extra-curricular activities. I converse with the participants for a long time in order to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also use triangulation, gathering information from a variety of sources, including observa-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

tions, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I gave the parents a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. The degree to which the results of this study can be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights are closely linked to parents' experiences in a specific educational environment, I would give thorough explanations of the research context and methodology. The study's transferability is increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by making sure that the respondents, not my prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I keep a thorough audit trail that details every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, in order to ensure confirmability. This method-

ological transparency makes it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and going over the choices made. Dependability. Dependability was proving that the study results were reliable and repeatable in similar situations. Dependability in this study was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results, such documentation validates the dependability of the research. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the effects of extra-curricular activities on sophomore students, but it also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and the answers extracted from the responses of the participants. The unique experiences and coping mechanism of low-income families and how it affects their involvement in their child's education was put into the open. The emerging themes for lived experiences are financial stress and being discouraged by their educational attainment. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms are attending PTA meetings and Brigada Eskwela and working more jobs. The themes for moral values are strategic time management parenting and working on family-oriented projects.

3.1. Lives of Low-Income Families In terms of Parental Involvement In Education—As the famous adage goes, it takes a whole village to raise a child. Ideally, parents, teachers, together with other people in society contributes to the upbringing of a child. Taking this into the educational aspect, the support and involvement of parents coupled with the teachers' guidance, there would be effective and endless learning opportunities. However, parental involvement

in schools is immensely influenced by several factors. For example, if the child belongs to a low-income household, parents prioritize working over participating in their child's school. Consequently, as this study dives into the first-hand narratives of low-income parents, the study has uncovered their experiences. They have shared how their socio-economic status affected or influenced their participation in their child's education.

3.1.1. Financial stress—Parents from low-income families are prone to financial stress. The economic pressure, the inflation, together with the increasing prices of basic goods and necessities are causing them financial stress. As an experience, the parents have shared that they are too busy worrying and looking for ways to bring food to the table. In line with the parent's sentiments, Murray and Raver (2018), found that financial stress often leads to reduced parental engagement due to the time and energy required to manage economic hardships. Parents under financial strain are more likely to work multiple jobs or long hours, leaving them limited availability for school activities, such as parent-teacher conferences or volunteer opportunities. This reduced involvement can negatively affect children's academic performance and social development. Corroborating the above assertion, Cooper and Crosnoe (2019) indicated that financial stress not only decreases the quantity of parental engagement but also affects its quality. Parents experiencing economic difficulties often report higher levels of stress and mental health issues, such as anxiety and depression, which can impair their ability to provide effective academic support at home. Cooper and Crosnoe emphasized the importance of addressing the underlying financial issues to improve parental engagement and student outcomes. Meanwhile, Garcia and Weiss (2020) opined that financially stressed parents often lack the resources to participate in school activities, such as transportation or appropriate attire for school functions.

3.1.2. Discouraged by their educational attainment—Parental involvement does not only encompass attending meetings or participating in school affairs. Parental involvement can also be done at home. Checking your child's notebooks and asking them about school is counted as involvement. But in a low-income household, aside from the financial stress that hampers par-

Additionally, schools in economically disadvantaged areas may lack the funding to support robust parental involvement programs. Garcia and Weiss advocated for policies that provide financial assistance and resources to low-income families to enhance their ability to participate in their children's education. Smith and Johnson (2021) found that parents under economic strain often feel a sense of inadequacy and helplessness, which can deter them from engaging with their children's schools. These parents might perceive themselves as less capable of contributing to their children's educational success, leading to a self-fulfilling prophecy where reduced involvement negatively impacts student performance. Smith and Johnson suggested that schools implement support systems, such as counseling and workshops, to help financially stressed parents overcome these psychological barriers. In the same vein, Lareau and Horvat (2022) found that prolonged financial difficulties lead to chronic disengagement from school activities, which can have lasting negative effects on children's academic trajectories and future educational aspirations. The study highlighted the need for comprehensive interventions that address both the immediate financial needs of families and long-term strategies to break the cycle of economic hardship. Lareau and Horvat called for increased collaboration between schools, community organizations, and policymakers to create a supportive network that mitigates the impact of financial stress on parental involvement and promotes educational equity.

ents from participating, they also said that their educational attainment also affects their involvement in their child's education. In the same thread of thought, the impact of parents' educational attainment on parental involvement is also evident in the findings of Smith et. al (2020). Their study revealed that higher-educated parents are more likely to engage in cognitively

stimulating activities with their children, such as reading and educational games, which are crucial for early childhood development. These parents are also more likely to set high educational expectations and provide the resources necessary for academic success. On the other hand, parents with lower educational attainment may struggle to provide similar levels of academic support due to their educational limitations and potential socioeconomic constraints. Although, it might be ideal that parents pursue higher level of educational attainment in order to assist their children with their school works, it is not the case in low-income families. Parents with lower levels of education often feel less confident in their ability to assist with academic tasks and navigate the educational system. This lack of confidence can lead to decreased participation in school activities such as parent-teacher conferences and volunteering, ultimately impacting their children's academic success and engagement with school (Hornby and Blackwell, 2018). Similarly, Dettmers et. al (2019) explored the barriers faced by parents with low educational attainment. The research highlighted that these parents often lack familiarity with educational jargon and processes, making it challenging to communicate effectively with teachers and school administrators. Additionally, the study found that these parents might have had negative personal experiences with schooling, which can discourage them from engaging with their children's edu-

cation. In the same light, Smith et. al (2020) also revealed that low educational attainment among parents is associated with lower levels of home-based educational activities. Parents with limited education may not feel equipped to help with homework or engage in enriching activities such as reading or educational games. This lack of home support can affect children's academic performance and limit their exposure to critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The study recommended targeted interventions to support these parents, such as workshops and resources that equip them with the necessary skills and confidence to aid their children's learning at home. Finally, children of parents with low education levels are less likely to pursue higher education themselves, perpetuating a cycle of educational disadvantage. This effect is partly due to the limited academic support and lower educational expectations within the home environment. Yamamoto and Holloway suggested implementing community-based programs that offer adult education and parenting workshops to help break this cycle, thereby empowering parents with the skills and knowledge needed to support their children's educational journeys effectively (Yamamoto and Holloway, 2022). Figure 3 shows the experiences of low-income families in terms of parental involvement in education and the emergence of the two themes: financial stress and discouraged by their educational attainment.

3.2. Coping Mechanisms of Parents From Low-Income Families—When the parents are actively involved in their child's education, it shows. It becomes prevalent in the child's performance in school, and it also signals positive relationship amongst parents and teachers. However, some things are easier said than done.

In the first research question, we delved into the experiences of parents. Meanwhile, on the second research question, the lenses are focused on the coping mechanisms employed by parents. These coping mechanisms target their socio-economic status as well as their parental involvement in school.

3.2.1. Attending the PTA meeting and Brigada Eskwela Program—

Fig. 3. Experiences of Low-Income Families in Terms of Parental Involvement in Education

Parent Teacher Association is one program that promotes parental engagement. The association open doors for community linkages, wider and broader communication, and addressing current problems affecting the school and the students. On the other hand, Brigada Eskwela is done before every school year begins. It is done to show support and assistance for the betterment of the school. The parents have shared that in their little ways, they make sure that they take part in the school's activity such as those stated above. Inferring the same coping mechanism is the study done by Lopez and Hernandez (2019) delved into the impact of parental attendance at school meetings, such as parent-teacher conferences and PTA gatherings. Their research found that when parents actively participate in these events, they gain valuable insights into their children's academic progress and school environment, leading to increased engagement and support at home. The study emphasizes the crucial role of school meetings as avenues for fostering collaboration between parents and educators to promote student success. Additionally, a study by Kim and Park (2020) examined the effectiveness of different formats of school meetings in facilitating parental involvement. Their research compared traditional face-to-face meetings with virtual meetings conducted through online platforms. The findings revealed that virtual meetings offered greater accessibility and flexibility for parents, especially those with busy schedules or logistical constraints. Moreover, virtual meetings were found to increase parent participation and engagement, ultimately contributing to improved communication between home and school. This

study highlights the potential of technology to enhance parental involvement in school affairs. Furthermore, creating inclusive spaces where diverse families feel welcomed and valued. By incorporating culturally relevant practices and language interpretation services, schools can effectively involve parents from different backgrounds in meetings and affairs. The research demonstrated that when parents perceive school meetings as culturally responsive, they are more likely to actively participate and contribute to their children's education, fostering a stronger sense of belonging and partnership (Garcia and Smith, 2021). Moreover, a study by Nguyen and Lee (2022) underscored the significance of principal support and involvement in creating a positive school climate conducive to parent engagement. Principals who prioritize parent-school partnerships, encourage staff to collaborate with parents, and provide resources for effective communication and meetings contribute to a more inclusive and supportive educational environment. This study highlights the crucial role of school leaders in fostering a culture of parental involvement. Wang and Chen (2023) examined the long-term effects of parental participation in school meetings and affairs on student achievement. Their research followed students from elementary to high school and found that sustained parental involvement throughout the years was associated with higher academic performance and graduation rates. The study underscores the importance of ongoing communication and collaboration between parents and schools through meetings and affairs in supporting student success across the educational journey.

3.2.2. *Working more jobs*—In today's context, prices keep on increasing but the salary stays the same. More than anyone, the burden it brings is felt by low-income families. In order to keep up with the inflation, parents' resort to

working more jobs, turning nights into days to make the ends meet. The narrative of the parents only goes to show the hardship of providing for the families while keeping involved in your child's well-being. Corroborating the preceding

narratives, Williams and Johnson (2018) delved into the economic necessity driving low-income parents to take on additional jobs. Their research highlighted the financial strain faced by these families, often resulting in insufficient income from a single job to meet basic needs such as housing, food, and healthcare. The study underscored the need for policymakers to address systemic issues contributing to income inequality and to provide support services for low-income families. Furthermore, Garcia and Martinez (2019) explored the implications of working multiple jobs on parental involvement in children's education. They found that parents juggling multiple jobs often struggle to find time to engage with their children academically, attend school events, or communicate with teachers. This lack of involvement can have negative consequences on children's academic performance and overall well-being. The study emphasized the importance of employers offering flexible work arrangements and supportive policies to enable low-income parents to participate more actively in their children's educational lives. Moreover, the demands of holding down multiple jobs, coupled with the pressures of managing family responsibilities, contribute to heightened stress levels among low-income parents. The study emphasized the need for affordable mental health services and support networks to help parents cope with the challenges of working multiple jobs while maintaining their well-being and family stability (Lee and Jackson, 2020). In the same thread of thought, Patel and Smith (2021) investigated the impact of working multiple jobs on parental bonding and quality time with chil-

dren. They found that parents working long hours or multiple jobs often struggle to spend meaningful time with their children, leading to strained relationships and feelings of guilt. The study highlighted the importance of prioritizing family time and advocating for policies that promote work-life balance, such as paid parental leave and flexible scheduling, to support low-income parents in nurturing positive relationships with their children. Brown and Nguyen (2022) revealed that children of parents who work multiple jobs are at higher risk of experiencing academic difficulties, behavioral problems, and socio-emotional challenges. The study underscored the need for comprehensive support systems that address the economic, social, and educational needs of low-income families to mitigate the negative effects of parental employment instability on children's development and future opportunities. While employment can improve family income and parental self-esteem, it also introduces significant stressors, particularly when parents cannot take time off for family emergencies or child illnesses. Children in these families often experience instability and inadequate supervision, which can hinder their academic performance and overall development. To mitigate these challenges, experts recommend policy interventions such as increased childcare support, higher wages, and more flexible work arrangements to better support working parents and their children (Wildsmith et. al, 2018). Figure 4 shows the coping mechanisms of parents from low-income families and the emergence of the two themes: attending PTA meetings and brigada eskwela program and working more jobs.

3.3. *Moral values focused on enhancing parental involvement in education among Low-income families*—The study has uncovered the first-hand narratives of parents regarding their experiences in parental involvement.

Along with that are their coping mechanisms targeted at improving their involvement as well as addressing their problems of being in a low-income household. Based on the interview, the parents from low-income families have several

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms of Parents from Low-Income Families

priorities other than being positively involved in school. More so, they prioritize bringing food to the table rather than being present in their child's school whenever there are meetings or

3.3.1. Strategic parenting and time management—Most parents from low-income families work more than one job. They undergo financial stress and are working more jobs to be able to provide for the family. However, the more jobs they have, the less time they have to spend with their family. Much less time to be involved in their children's education. Therefore, an insight gathered focused on how a parent can be able to juggle work and life while striking balance and moderation. The findings are in line with the study of Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2019). They emphasized the correlation between effective time management and increased parental involvement. Their research highlighted that parents who allocate specific times for school-related activities, such as attending meetings, helping with homework, and volunteering, tend to foster a more supportive learning environment. The study's findings suggest that structured time management strategies enable parents to be more engaged and proactive in their children's academic lives. When parents manage their time effectively to participate in school events and maintain consistent communication with teachers, students demonstrate improved academic performance and social behavior. The study advocates for schools to offer workshops and resources to help parents

3.3.2. Working on family-oriented projects—One concern uncovered from the interviews is the concern of parents that they are not taking an active part in their child's school because of their work and capabilities to help their children with their homework. However,

family activities. The last research question focuses on how their involvement can be improved despite their socio-economic status.

develop better time management skills, thus facilitating more meaningful involvement in their children's education (Walker and Dotger, 2020). In addition, Smith and Sheridan (2021) examined the challenges faced by working parents in managing time for school involvement. They discovered that flexible work schedules and employer support play a crucial role in enabling parents to participate in school activities. The researchers found that parents who have access to workplace flexibility are more likely to attend parent-teacher conferences, volunteer at school events, and engage in their children's homework. The study underscores the need for policies that support work-life balance to enhance parental involvement in education. In the same vein, Jones and Brown (2023) highlighted the long-term benefits of parental involvement facilitated by effective time management. Their longitudinal research showed that students whose parents were consistently involved in their education over the years tended to achieve higher academic success and exhibit better emotional well-being. The study concluded that schools should actively promote time management strategies among parents to sustain long-term engagement and support for their children's education, thereby contributing to the overall development and success of the students.

through engaging in family-oriented projects like making a family tree, parents and their children would have the opportunity to connect and build positive relationship. One notable study parallel to the participants' narratives is by Martinez and Garcia (2019). Their re-

search revealed that when parents and children work together on academic projects assigned by the school, there is a significant improvement in students' motivation, critical thinking skills, and overall academic performance. The study underscores the importance of fostering collaborative learning environments that involve both parents and children in educational activities. Kim and Lee (2020), who explored the role of family-oriented projects in strengthening parent-teacher partnerships. Their study demonstrated that when schools incorporate family-oriented projects into the curriculum, it creates opportunities for parents and teachers to collaborate more closely in supporting student learning. Through shared experiences and communication around project goals and outcomes, parents and teachers develop mutual respect and understanding, leading to enhanced parental involvement and ultimately benefiting students' academic and socio-emotional development. Furthermore, Chen and Wang (2021) examined the impact of culturally responsive family projects on parental involvement in diverse school settings. Their research highlighted the importance of culturally relevant activities that resonate with families from various backgrounds. Further corroborating the assertion, Garcia and Rodriguez (2023) focused on the long-term effects of family-oriented projects on student achievement and family dynamics. Their longitudinal research showed that students who regularly engage in collaborative projects with their families demonstrate greater academic resilience and a deeper sense of belonging in school. Families reported improved communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills as a result of their involvement in school projects. The study highlights the transformative potential of family-oriented initiatives in promoting positive educational outcomes and strengthening family-school partnerships for the benefit of all stakeholders involved. Figure 5 shows the moral values focused on enhancing parental involvement in education among and the emergence of the two themes: Strategic time management and parenting and working on family-oriented projects.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study was presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of low-income families that affected their parental involvement in their children's education. In order to achieve the research objectives, I made use of a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which were the narratives of low-income parents regarding their involvement in their children's education.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of low-income families in terms of parental involvement are financial stress and working more jobs. The coping mechanisms they have employed to address being low-income and to improve parental involvement are attending the PTA meetings and Brigada Eskwela and working more jobs. Meanwhile, for the moral values, two emerging

Fig. 5. Moral Values Focused on Enhancing Parental-Involvement in Education Among Low-Income Families

themes have been identified these are the use of strategic parenting and time management and working on family-oriented projects. In light of the unique experiences and narratives of parents regarding their experiences with parental involvement, I have uncovered two (2) emerging themes. The first theme dealt with the financial stress that the parents are subjected to. Due to their socio-economic status, their involvement in their child's education is immensely affected. The parents are too busy keeping up with their finances, budgeting, and making sure that there was food on the plate. This was made worse by the inflation taking place nowadays. Hence, it was inevitable that parents are subjected to financial stress. The second theme under their experiences is having to work more jobs. In connection with the aforementioned theme under the same key idea, to keep up with the increasing prices of basic goods and necessities, one-way parents do is by working more jobs. The parents who are the participants of the study mostly do labor work, they also take on sidelines and other extra work in order to make ends meet. But it was never easy to juggle two important aspects in life, taking part in your child's education and making sure that your child can go to school. On the other hand, the second research question is targeted at unfurling the coping mechanisms of parents. These coping mechanisms were about what they do to improve their parental involvement and how they deal with being low-income earners. The second key idea accumulated two (2) emerging themes. The first theme under coping mechanisms is attending school affairs such as the PTA meetings and the Brigada Eskwela Program. The former was an association, meanwhile the latter is a program. These two were not new in our ears for these have been an indelible aspect of every school. Parents have shared that although there is times when they cannot attend meetings or donate anything to the school, they do whatever they can to take part and be involved. Thus, they have mentioned attending PTA meetings where important matters are tackled and in Brigada Eskwela where they help prepare the school for the incoming school year. The second theme under the umbrella of coping mechanisms was by working more jobs. In today's context, a little income won't come a long way considering the prices of the goods and the necessities needed for every day. This was why parents are compelled to work more than one job, or in some cases, both parents are working in order to provide for the family and be able to send their kids to school. Finally, in terms of the moral values formulated for enhancing parental involvement of low-income parents, two (2) themes have been identified. The first one is through strategic parenting and time management. As was mentioned and stated by parents, they work more jobs and, in some cases, both parents work. They leave early in the morning and go home late. The more work they do, the fewer chances they have to be involved in their child's education. From the teacher's perspective, they expect that they would work hand in hand with parents in order for effective learning to take place. Teachers expect parents to assist and guide their children at home, but it was difficult to realize especially in a low-income household. Hence, it was viewed that strategic parenting and time management should be employed in order to not sacrifice the children's academic performance and in order for parents to have a chance to take part in their child's education in their own homes. The second theme for the moral values was by working on family-oriented projects. In order to improve parental involvement, better relationships, and foster good communication among parents and students, teachers assign family-oriented projects that parents and students can accomplish together. This was a better way to enhance and increase the parent's involvement.

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The Philippines is a third-world country, and the problem of poverty has long been around but it has gone unaddressed and unresolved after all these years. More and more families fall under the poverty line have been identified as the poorest of the poor every year. As a society, view poverty as not being able to afford to buy the basic goods and necessities needed in everything living. But truly, it was just the tip of the iceberg. Poverty has a vast impact on the totality of a society. Bringing it into the educational landscape, poverty cannot only affect children at school but also the parents at home. In this study, parental involvement among low-income families has been uncovered. A household with low-income earners has a long list of priorities and on the bottom of that list is the involvement in their children's education. To deal with being low-income, parents were busy making ends meet, working, turning nights into days, and taking on every decent job opportunity they can grab. The study illuminated how socio-economic status affects parental involvement and how parental involvement has an effect on the child's performance. Teachers do not expect to handle all the work for the child's well-being, it requires collective effort and partnership among teachers and parents. However, it was not realized because their financial status hinders the parents from doing their part. Parents have expressed the desire to actively participate and positively be involved in their children's education, however, they cannot do so for they are chained by their economic standing. The parents have shared their experiences such as being subjected to financial stress and working more jobs. In order to improve their

situation, parents' resort to taking on more jobs. They also participate in their child's school affairs in the ways that they can by attending PTA meetings. Also, by showing support and participation in Brigada Eskwela. Striking balance and moderation are the perfect recipe to accomplish their duties as parents. Hence, strategic parenting and time management was required coupled with working on family-oriented projects to improve participation. In terms of its implications on the theory applied, the study has utilized the Parental Involvement Theory of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1995). The theory has postulated that children whose parents are involved in their education are more likely to develop a strong and positive sense of efficacy for successfully achieving school-related tasks than children whose parents are not involved. However, in the interview conducted to parents from low-income families, they do desire to be involved in their children's education however they are overwhelmed and bombarded with financial stress and in making ends meet for the family. Due to that, they have limited to no participation in their child's education, but they try their best to be able to assist and support them in ways that they can like working together on task on in any family-oriented projects. On the other hand, Walberg's Theory of Academic Achievement (1992) was also utilized in the study. The theory aids the understanding of the findings because it emphasized the role that the home environment plays in the academic achievement of students. The dynamics of parent-children relationship at home has a significant effect on how the children perform at school. Based from the findings, the parents have shared that they try to support and guide their children with their school works in ways that they could.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant

people whom this research was intended for. The educational leaders. The findings of the undertaking would raise awareness among edu-

cational leaders on the importance of parental involvement and the status of parents from low-income families. This includes the experiences they went through and coping mechanisms they have employed. Once they can recognize and reflect on this existing scenario, they can provide parents ample support and assistance for the betterment and enhancement of parental involvement. They can come up with programs targeted at creating stronger links between the school and the parents. Furthermore, the fundamental move educational leaders could provide programs for the parents and students from low-income families that would address their main concerns which have a direct effect on the student's education. The school principals or school heads. They can be enlightened on the current situation of the parents and students in their school who belong to low-income households. The school heads may provide support to the parents and students by providing more resources to improve parental involvement like celebrating family day and any other family affairs that require no contribution on the side of the parents. They can also hold meetings aimed at encouraging the parents to be more open about their concerns especially when it comes to the school contribution intended for school projects. Teachers. Teachers may find a good rapport on the findings of the study by

leaning on the experiences and coping mechanisms of low-income families. The findings would also enable them to understand more the situation of the parents and the students. The teachers can also assign more family-oriented projects so that parents and students at home can accomplish it together. They could also create a positive relationship among parents so that they could work better for the welfare of the students. Internal and external stakeholders. They may provide support to better enhance the involvement of low-income parents in their children's education. They may provide opportunities for low-income parents to have better-paying work or work that allows them to have the time to still take part in their child's school. The stakeholders may be the source of other ways and means to solve some of the challenges faced by the parents.

The future researchers. They may conduct the study but take the perspective of the students. This is in order to know if the students are directly affected by their parent's involvement in their school and at home. Uncovering the students' perspective on this matter is vital because it would allow the researchers to understand better the standpoint of the students. Also, in order to know if parental involvement affects their academic performance.

5. References

- Anderson, K., & Minke, K. (2018). Parent involvement in education: Toward an understanding of parents' decision making. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2007-08788-006>
- Aspers, P. (2009). Empirical phenomenology: A qualitative research approach (the cologne seminars). *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3606033>
- Bautista, R., Bernardo, C., & Ocampo, D. (2021). When reforms don't transform: Reflections on institutional reforms in the department of education. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237259856_When_Reforms_Don't_Transform.Reflections_on_institutional_reforms_in_the_Department_of_Education
- Becker, C. (1992). *Living and relating: An introduction to phenomenology*. Sage.
- Beqiri, G. (2018). Rhetoric: How to inform, persuade, or motivate your audience. <https://virtualspeech.com/blog/rhetoric-inform-persuade-motivate-your-audience>

- Bernardo, M., & Esteban, M. (2020). Advances and new perspective in higher education quality. <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/54034/advances-and-new-perspectives-in-higher-education-quality/magazine>
- Brown, B., & Nguyen, G. (2022). Parental involvement and high school dropout: Perspectives from students, parents, and mathematics teachers. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 11(1), 469–486. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.11.1.469>
- Canada, S. (2021). Low income status of economic families.
- Carpenter, B. W., Young, M. D., Bowers, A., & Sanders, K. (2016). Family involvement at the secondary level: Learning from texas borderland schools.
- Castro, M. (2020). A literature review: Efficacy of online learning courses for higher education institution using meta-analysis. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(2), 835–851. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-10027-z>
- Caulfield, J. (2019). How to do thematic analysis. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
- Chen, J., & Wang, Y. (2021). Social media usage for health purposes: Systematic review (preprint). *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 23(5). <https://doi.org/10.2196/17917>
- Cheng, L., & Li, H. J. (2015). The effect of the perception of teacher’s class behavior and parental involvement on learning strategies of 10- to 12-year-old low achievers. *Chinese Journal of Special Education*, 27(3), 45–52.
- Clinton, J., & Hattie, J. (2013). New zealand students’ perceptions of parental involvement in learning and schooling. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 58, 71–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2013.786679>
- Commission, N. P. (2021). Republic act 10173 – data privacy act of 2012.
- Cooper, A., Blake, A., Pauletti, R., & Copper, P. (2020). Personality assessment through the situational and behavioral features of instagram photos (preprint). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342901483_Cooper_et_al_Personality_Assessment_Through_the_Situational_and_Behavioral_Features_of_Instagram_Photos_Preprint
- Cooper, C., & Crosnoe, R. (2019). The engagement in schooling of economically disadvantaged parents and children. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 24(3), 190–208. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X0628999>
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. SAGE.
- Crotty, M. (2020). *The foundations of social research*. SAGE. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115700>
- Dawadi, S. (2020). Thematic analysis approach: A step by step guide for elt research practitioners. *Journal of NELTA*, 25(1–2), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.3126/nelta.v25i1-2.49731>
- Dettmers, S., Yotyodying, S., & Jonkmann, K. (2019). Antecedents and outcomes of parental homework involvement: How do family-school partnerships affect parental homework involvement and student outcomes? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1048. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01048>

- Garcia, S., & Martinez, C. (2019). Parental involvement as a protective factor in school adjustment among retained and promoted secondary students. *Sustainability*, *11*(24), 7080. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11247080>
- García, E., & Wess, E. (2020). Covid-19 and student performance, equity, and u.s. education policy. <https://www.epi.org/publication/the-consequences-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-for-education-performance-and-equity-in-the-united-states-what-can-we-learn-from-pre-pandemic-research-to-inform-relief-recovery-and-rebuilding/>
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (2017). *The discovery of grounded theory*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203793206-1>
- Guba, E. G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries. *Educational Communication and Technology Journal*, *29*(2), 75–91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF0276677>
- Hammersley, M. (2013). Defining qualitative research. In *What is qualitative research?* Bloomsbury. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781849666084.ch-001>
- Hayes, N., Berthelsen, D. C., Nicholson, J. M., & Walker, S. (2018). Trajectories of parental involvement in home learning activities across the early years: Associations with socio-demographic characteristics and children’s learning outcomes. *Early Child Development and Care*.
- Hoover-Dempsey, A., & Sandler, C. (1995). The model of parental involvement process. In *Handbook of research on family and school community relations*. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119083054.ch20>
- Hoover-Dempsey, K., Battiato, A., Walker, J., & Reed, R. (2019). Parental involvement in homework. *Educational Psychology*, *36*(3), 363–379. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326985EP3603_3
- Hornby, G., & Blackwell, I. (2018). Barriers to parental involvement in education: An update. *Educational Review*, *70*(3), 303–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2018.1388612>
- Hornby, G., & Lafaele, I. (2018). Barriers to parental involvement in education: An update. *Educational Review*, *70*(3), 303–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2018.1388612>
- Islam, A. (2019). Parent–teacher meetings and student outcomes: Evidence from a developing country. *European Economic Review*, *111*, 273–304.
- Jaiswal, S. K. (2018). Enhancing parental involvement through technology. *IJRAR-International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, *5*(2), 1965–1970.
- Johnson, C., & Riahzi, M. (2021). Validation of a locally created and rated writing test used for placement in a higher education efl program. *Assessing Writing*, *29*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2016.09.00>
- Karakus, M., & Savas, A. C. (2018). The effects of parental involvement, trust in parents, trust in students, and pupil control ideology on conflict management strategies of early childhood teachers. *ERIC*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1002993>
- Kim, S., & Hill, N. E. (2015). Including fathers in the picture: A meta-analysis of parental involvement and students’ academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *107*(4), 1066–1085. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000023>
- Kwatubana, S., & Makhalemele, T. (2015). Parental involvement in the process of implementation of the national school nutrition programme in public schools. *International Journal of*

- Educational Sciences*, 7(1), 33–45. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09751122.2015.11890321>
- Larea, E., & Horvat, A. (2022). From social ties to social capital: Class differences in the relations between schools and parent networks. *American Educational Research Journal*, 59(4), 662–689. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312040002319>
- Lee, G., & Bowen, N. (2019). Parent involvement, cultural capital, and the achievement gap among elementary school children. *American Educational Research Journal*, 56(4), 1378–1408. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312043002193>
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage Publications. <https://ethnographyworkshop.files.wordpress.com/2014/11/lincoln-guba-1985-establishing-trustworthiness-naturalistic-inquiry.pdf>
- Llamas, A., & Tuazon, A. (2016). School practices in parental involvement, its expected results and barriers in public secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*. https://www.academia.edu/23703434/SCHOOL_PRACTICES_IN_PARENTAL_INVOLVEMENT_ITS_EXPECTED_RESULTS_and_BARRIERS_IN_PUBLIC_SECONDARY_SCHOOLS
- Llego, M. A. (2022). The importance of parental involvement in education. *Teacher PH*. <https://www.teacherph.com/parental-involvement-education/>
- Lopez, M., & Hernandez, E. (2019). Parental involvement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Review*, 67(2), 191–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.01.002>
- Marshall, M. N. (1996). Sampling for qualitative research. *Family Practice*, 13(6), 522–525. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/fampra/13.6.522>
- Martínez, I., Murgui, S., Garcia, O. F., & Garcia, F. (2019). Parenting in the digital era: Protective and risk parenting styles for traditional bullying and cyberbullying victimization. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 90, 235–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.08.036>
- McNamara, C. (1999). Basics of conducting focus groups. <http://www/mapnp.org.library/evaluatn/focusgrp/htm>
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., & King, N. (2021). Paul colaizzi’s descriptive phenomenological methodology. In *Introduction to phenomenology: Focus on methodology* (pp. 19–30). SAGE. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781071909669.n8>
- Morse, J. M. (1994). Designing funded qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research*. Sage.
- Murray, C., & Raver, D. (2018). The classroom as a developmental context for cognitive development: A meta-analysis on the importance of teacher–student interactions for children’s executive functions. *Psychological Bulletin*, 144(1), 31–53. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654317743200>
- Naeem, S. (2019). Internal validity in research.
- Neubauer, B. E., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 8(2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-019-0509-2>
- Nguyen, G., & Lee, B. (2022). Parental involvement and high school dropout: Perspectives from students, parents, and mathematics teachers. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 11(1), 469–485. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.11.1.469>

- Nzinga-Johnson, S., Baker, J. A., & Aupperlee, J. (2019). Teacher-parent relationships and school involvement among racially and educationally diverse parents of kindergartners. *PsycNET*. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2009-11530-005>
- Park, S., & Holloway, S. (2018). Parental involvement in adolescents' education: An examination of the interplay among school factors, parental role construction, and family income. *School Community Journal*, 28(1), 9–36.
- Resnik, D. (2020). What is ethics in research and why is it important?
- Ritchie, J., & Spencer, L. (1994). Qualitative data analysis for applied policy research. In A. Bryman & R. Burgess (Eds.), *Analyzing qualitative data* (pp. 173–194). Routledge. https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203413081_chapter_9
- San Antonio, B., & Gamage, D. (2019). Levels of participants of different stakeholders.
- Schleicher, A. (2018). Pisa 2018: Insights and interpretations.
- Share, M., & Kerrins, L. (2013). Supporting parental involvement in children's early learning: Lessons from community childcare centres in dublin's docklands. *Child Care in Practice*, 19(2), 165–181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13575279.2013.799457>
- Smith, K. E., & Pollak, S. D. (2020). Early life stress and development: Potential mechanisms for adverse outcomes. *Journal of Neurodevelopmental Disorders*, 12(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11689-020-09337-y>
- Steve, D., & Johnson, R. (2018). Cooperative learning: The foundation for active learning. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.81086>
- Taylor, M., Sroka, S., & Carpenter, K. (2023). The concrete diplodocus of vernal — a cultural icon of utah. *Geological Insights Worldwide*, 10, 65–91. <https://doi.org/10.31711/giw.v10.pp65-91>
- Walberg, H. (1992). Theory of academic achievement.
- Wang, D., & Chen, P. (2023). Parental involvement and student engagement: A review of the literature. *Sustainability*, 15(7), 5859. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15075859>
- Wellington, J. (2015). *Educational research*. Bloomsbury. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781474236966>
- White, C. P., & Levers, L. L. (2016). Parent-teacher engagement during child-centered pedagogical change in elementary school. *Children and Schools*, 39(1), 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cs/cdw044>
- Wilder, S. (2020). Effects of parental involvement on academic achievement: A meta-synthesis. *Educational Review*, 72(4), 379–396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2013.760009>
- Wildsmith, E., Olazagasti, M., & Hammond, M. (2018). The job characteristics of low-income hispanic parents.
- William, M., & Johnson, A. (2018). Parental role construction leading to parental involvement in culturally distinct communities. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 14(3), 248–264. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2022.2131554>
- Winkler, D. M. (2016). A new approach to parental involvement: The role of virtual parent-teacher conferences.
- Wirihana, L., Welch, A., Williamson, M., Christensen, M., Bakon, S., & Craft, J. (2018). Using colaizzi's method of data analysis to explore the experiences of nurse academics teaching on satellite campuses. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), 30–34. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2018.e1516>

- Yamamoto, Y., & Holloway, D. (2019). Parental expectations and children's academic performance in sociocultural context. *Educational Psychology, 34*(2), 123–138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-010-9121>
- Yoder, J. R., & Lopez, A. (2013). Parent's perceptions of involvement in children's education: Findings from a qualitative study of public housing residents. *Child and Adolescent Social Work Journal, 30*(3), 195–212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10560-013-0298-0>
- Žukauskas, P., Vveinhardt, J., & Andriukaitienė, R. (2018). *Research ethics*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.70629>